

FAIR in Register Based Research

Statistics Denmark (SD) and The Danish Health Data Authority (SDS)

Research Service

SDS and DST provide access to microdata for research purposes

Data is free of charge – but you pay for the service to provide access

Most costumers are returning costumers – often from research institutions, but also outside research

Service includes advice on relevant data for the project in question, hence there is an element of datastewardship involved.

In the years to come the need for competences at DST/SDS is expected to develop as datastewardship spreads across the users and new needs arise.

Statistics vs. microdata

SDS and DST deliver access to microdata as well as support for users of more aggregated statistics. Aggregated statistics include:

Danish Health Data Authority

- Publications on new data – publically available
- eSundned (online service with possibility of crafting specific statistics)
 - Publically available version
 - Closed version aimed at public authorities (municipalities and regions)
- Forskerservice – support for costumized statistics
- Presence on social media.

Statistics Denmark

- Publications on new data – publically available
- Statistikbanken (online service with possibility of crafting specific statistics) – publically available
- DST Consulting – support for costumized statistics
- DST Survey – support for costumized surveys
- Presence on social media.

What types of microdata are available?

Most data from official registers – some from surveys (DST)

Registers are typically set up for other purposes than analyses

Danish Health Data Authority

National Health Registries

- Diseases, medicine, and patient treatment
- Pregnancy, births, and children
- Causes of death and biological material
- Treatment wills and organ donation
- Health economics and financing

Statistics Denmark

Socio-economic registers, e.g.:

- Population
- Education
- Income
- Social status
- Crime
- Corporate data
- Taxation
- ...and some health data

Confidentiality

- Microdata available from DST and SDS – typically – include confidential information on individuals or individual companies.
- Access to microdata data requires an approval from the organisation in question.
 - DST requires authorisation of the relevant institution and certification of the individual user.
 - SDS also require approval by the users. Users must be associated with an authorized research environment. Registered users will subsequently have access to microdata on the projects they are associated with. The project descriptions specify which data the project can access.
- DST and SDS offer access to pseudonomised microdata.
- In some cases SDS also offer access to microdata including CPR—numbers. Access to microdata with CPR information requires, in addition to compliance with the general rules and procedure in force, that it is not possible to carry out the planned analyses/actions with data in the protected environment in SDS, for technical or other reasons that can be documented.
- SDS and DST also differ in the sense that DST only offers access to microdata for research and analysis, whereas SDS offer access for administrative purposes
- SDS and DST both have the opportunity to sanction users that do not comply with the access rules – as well as their employers (institutions). For this reason DST and SDS only allows authorization of Danish institutions/institutions located in Denmark

Where can I work on the microdata

SDS

Microdata can be assessed on SDS research machine, an online remote access to pseudonymized data from Danish health registers.

In special cases, it is possible to have data extracted from SDS research machine. After the approval procedure has been completed, data can be delivered to another data processing site. Data can either be download as an encrypted file, or data can be sent directly to Statistics Denmark via a secure connection.

DST

Microdata from Statistics Denmark must not leave DST. Hence, users must forward other external data to DST, where it is combined with DST-data and pseudonimised. Then it can be accessed on one of the following online platforms:

- DST's research maschine
- A hosted server at DST
- From 1. November 2022 a DST controlled part of an HPC

Data Management Plans vs. Project descriptions

Data Management Plans are often used for data generating projects in research environments.

When applying for data from DST and SDS, the focus is on project descriptions.

They do have similarities with DMPs, but the focus is on :

- The purpose of the project
- The societal and/or scientific value of the project
- The data needed (registers and variables)

Project descriptions allow researchers, at a later stage, to reconstruct the data used for the purpose specified in the project descriptions.

The project descriptions could be further developed to fulfill the same role as data management plans, where relevant (typically at the research institution).

FAIR - Findable

Registerdata are indeed findable:

- SDS and DST both have substantial metadata – in structured formats. Without these it is impossible to find data.
- All metadata is publically available
- Research services have been set up to guide researchers to the needed data

Possible improvements:

- Metadata could be translated into English in order to improve findability (but it is very expensive)
- It could be relevant to investigate how register data based on public registers could live up to the FAIR principle, that (meta)data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers, and that metadata include the identifier of the data it describes. E.g. it could be an idea to make metadata and project descriptions more available for online searches
- SDS and DST already possess large amounts of data, and it could be relevant for universities and others to make their data more findable by including them on platforms at DST or SDS

FAIR - Accessible

Register data is accessible:

- Publically available metadata make microdata from SDS and DST accessible
- Research Support offices provide access to data
- DST and SDS provides an annual overview of projects (titles)
- Data itself is free, you pay for the service to make data available

Possible improvements:

- Students have limited access to data for their studies

FAIR - Interoperable

Registerdata is interoperable:

Data at SDS and DST is highly interoperable – also across SDS and DST

Data at SDS and DST can be combined with external data sources, e.g. data from the individual user.

Possible improvements:

Closer Nordic cooperation is needed – the countries are individually too small.

The FAIR-requirements refer to a need for vocabularies and references in metadata that are in line with FAIR principles. FAIR principles have not been used to set up metadata at DST and SDS, and hence there may be a need to consult these.

DSD and DSTs data typically come from Danish registers. Hence, very little is translated into English.

FAIR - Reusable

Register data are reusable:

Data has been gathered at DST and SDS in order to be used and reused.

We also work on e.g. 3. part replication for publication purposes (peer review)

Possible improvements:

It could be made easier to get information on previous project-setups, as inactive projects are erased (Rigsarkivet does require some projects to be saved – via the researcher)